

Balancing mediation secrets and justice: rethinking mediation confidentiality in England and Wales

Abstract

Confidentiality is a cornerstone of mediation, distinguishing it from litigation and enhancing its appeal as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism. A robust framework for mediation confidentiality encourages open communication between parties and facilitates negotiations, thereby increasing the likelihood of settlement. However, the extent to which mediation confidentiality is protected under common law, particularly in England and Wales, remains unclear and inconsistent.

Generally, courts are reluctant to interfere with mediation confidentiality. Yet, the absence of a distinct mediation privilege leaves the protection of confidential mediation communications vulnerable to judicial discretion and evolving public policy considerations.

Furthermore, the article addresses how mediation confidentiality can potentially impact legal practice, noting that overprotection may deter parties from revealing essential information during mediation, while insufficient protection could discourage participation altogether. Ultimately, the article concludes that a tailored statutory mediation privilege, modelled on successful international examples, would strengthen the legal foundation of mediation confidentiality while preserving the courts' ability to deliver fair outcomes. The proposed reforms would strike a balanced approach, ensuring that mediation remains an effective dispute-resolution mechanism without compromising the principles of fairness and justice.

1. Introduction

Confidentiality is an essential philosophical tenet¹ of mediation and a key feature that distinguishes it from litigation.² A well-drawn agreement to mediate creates a mutual obligation on the parties and the mediator to keep what emerges during a mediation confidential.³ Confidentiality makes mediation attractive to potential parties as it protects them from negative publicity and is essential for encouraging open negotiations. It also promotes settlement by providing the parties with a safe space to discuss their issues and solve them collaboratively.⁴

This article critically assesses the extent to which mediation confidentiality is protected and the gaps that remain in common law, focusing on England and Wales. It proposes possible reforms to strengthen confidentiality based on lessons learnt from jurisdictions such as Australia and the United States. A distinct mediation privilege would be a step in the right direction; however, necessary caveats that arise will be discussed.

2. Striking the right balance: Mediation Confidentiality as a “double-edged sword”

¹ Penny Brooker, *Mediation Law: Journal through Institutionalism to Juridification* (Routledge 2013) 185.

² Dorcas Quek Anderson, 'Piercing the Veil of Confidentiality in Mediation to Ensure Good Faith Participation: An Untenable Position?' (2019) 31 SAclJ 713, 713.

³ Tony Allen, *Mediation Law and Civil Practice* (3rd edn, Bloomsbury Publishing Plc 2024) 250.

⁴ Ronán Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation: Law and Regulation in Comparative Context* (1st edn, Cambridge University Press 2022) 246.

Ascertaining the extent of confidentiality in mediation involves balancing and weighing two competing public policy interests. First, the courts consider the public interest in encouraging parties to resolve their disputes outside the court system.⁵ This was summed up in *Field v Commissioner of Railways (NSW)*, where the High Court of Australia stated that the purpose of excluding admissions made by parties during negotiations from evidence is to enable free communication and avoid the embarrassment of their admissions being used as evidence subsequently.⁶

The second competing interest is ensuring that courts access the best possible evidence to enable a fair and just decision, as referred to in *AWA Ltd v. Daniels (t/a Deloitte Haskins & Sells)*⁷. In this case, the plaintiff's solicitors referred to the existence of specific documents at mediation. When mediation failed, the defendant's solicitors notified the plaintiff to produce those documents at trial. The plaintiff sought to have the notices set aside, but Rolfe J refused to do so. On appeal, Rogers CJ approved of Rolfe J's reasoning and observed that, in principle, it would be too easy to set aside otherwise admissible and factual evidence simply by saying something about it during the mediation process, even if the subject is irrelevant to the mediation discussion.⁸

This case highlights the challenges courts face to ensure they have the best possible admissible evidence. Notably, Anderson suggested that confidentiality within mediation is a “double-edged sword” because although it encourages open negotiations, it can also lead to unfair treatment of vulnerable parties or harm third parties’ interests.⁹

⁵ *ibid* 248.

⁶ *Field v. Commissioner of Railways (NSW)* 99 CLR 285, 291.

⁷ *AWA Ltd v. Daniels (t/a Deloitte Haskins & Sells)* (1992) 7 ACSR 463, 468.

⁸ *ibid*.

⁹ Anderson (n 2) 715.

The following issues also arise. First, parties may hold back from mentioning essential matters if they think they will be precluded from raising them again in subsequent proceedings if the mediation is unsuccessful.¹⁰ Second, there is also the risk of a party approaching mediation as a ‘pre-trial fishing expedition’, and revelations of fact made by the opponent can be used strategically against the disclosing party at trial.¹¹ Third, some commentators suggest that lawyers will discourage their clients from disclosing anything during mediation, fearing they may say something confidential that could prompt the other side to search for evidence to prove the underlying facts at trial.¹² If mediation confidentiality is too broad, it can sterilise too much evidence and seriously undermine the litigation or arbitral process, and if it is too narrow, it can discourage parties from entering mediation.¹³ Therefore, a delicate balance is needed between supporting mediation confidentiality and not freezing litigation.¹⁴

¹⁰ Bobette Wolski, 'Confidentiality and Privilege in Mediation: Concepts in Need of Better Regulation and Explanation' (2020) 43 UNSWLJ 1552, 1565.

¹¹ Wendy Harris and Melinda Shirley, ‘Confidentiality in court-annexed mediation, fact or fallacy?’ (1993) 13(6) Queensland Lawyer 221, 228.

¹² John Woodward, 'Walking the Tightrope: Exploring the Relationship between Confidentiality and Disputant Participation' (2019) 30(1) Australasian Dispute Resolution Journal 23, 28.

¹³ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 249.

¹⁴ Laurence Boulle, *Mediation: Principles, Process, Practice* (3rd edn, LexisNexis Butterworths 2011) 714.

3. Protecting Mediation Evidence

There are different approaches to protecting mediation evidence, the most straightforward being by creating a privilege.¹⁵ When no settlement is reached at the end of a mediation, evidence of potential offers or admissions made in good faith to settle is inadmissible in subsequent litigation relating to the dispute.¹⁶ This is referred to as ‘without prejudice’ privilege. This privilege applies regardless of whether litigation has commenced or if the parties expressly provided that their negotiations are without prejudice.¹⁷ In the English case of *Unilever plc v. The Proctor & Gamble Company*¹⁸, Walker LJ summarised seven exceptions to the ‘without prejudice’ privilege¹⁹. Further exceptions have been added to this as well.

In the case of ‘without prejudice’ negotiations resulting in a settlement, evidence of agreements and statements made are subsequently admissible in arbitral or judicial proceedings.²⁰ Such evidence can also be used for enforcement purposes if a dispute surrounds what has been settled.²¹ Further limitations²² to this privilege highlighted by Boule indicate that to make use of this privilege, parties must have the objective of achieving a

¹⁵ Ronán Feehily, 'Confidentiality in Commercial Mediation: A Fine Balance (Part 1)' [2015] J S Afr L 516, 518.

¹⁶ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 250.

¹⁷ *Rush & Tompkins Ltd v Greater London Council* [1989] 1 AC 1280, [1988] 3 WLR 939.

¹⁸ *Unilever plc v. The Proctor & Gamble Company* [1999] EWCA Civ 3027.

¹⁹ *ibid* [23].

²⁰ *Biala Pty Ltd v. Mallina Holdings Ltd* [1989] 15 ACLR 208.

²¹ Boule, *Mediation: Principles, Process, Practice* (n 14) 675.

²² *ibid*.

settlement, and courts can claim that reliance on the privilege was not in good faith if communications were not genuinely aimed at settlement.²³

Legal professional privilege is a type of confidentiality that arises between the mediator or lawyer and the client to protect the client's rights in case of subsequent litigation. It is a common law protection that covers documents and other communications arising from legal proceedings or giving or obtaining legal advice.²⁴

A contract is one of the oldest ways to protect confidentiality in mediation.²⁵ It offers the best chance to tailor confidentiality to specific commercial legal needs, but its enforcement relies on the relevant court. All parties, including the mediator, usually agree to a confidentiality agreement, which keeps the information disclosed during the mediation confidential.

Contractual confidentiality is also helpful in clarifying the existing law and the parties' intentions, especially regarding ambiguous or discretionary regulations.²⁶

4. Impact of the mediator's testimony on confidentiality

In *Farm Assist Ltd v Secretary of State for the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (No 2)*²⁷, the court ordered the mediator to testify because the disputing parties had waived their privilege. The court deemed the disclosure to be in the interest of justice. The mediation agreement contained a contractual clause stating that parties agreed not to call the mediator as a witness in any litigation or arbitration relating to the dispute. Despite this, Ramsey J

²³ *ibid* 676.

²⁴ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 256.

²⁵ Feehily, 'Confidentiality in Commercial Mediation' (n 15) 532.

²⁶ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 291.

²⁷ *Farm Assist Ltd v. Secretary of State for the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (No 2)* [2009] EWHC 1102 (TCC), [2009] All ER (D) 228.

decided that the parties were entitled to waive their privilege. The mediator's right to rely on the confidentiality clause was also overridden by the interest of justice here.

Briggs LJ summarised the concerning impact of this legal position, writing that it is of widespread concern that confidentiality in mediation is limited to that conferred by the 'without prejudice' principle and if attempts to widen it contractually are ineffective, mediation will lose one of its main attractions as a dispute resolution mechanism.²⁸

Overreliance on contractual confidentiality provisions found in mediation agreements can be problematic if public policy calls for these provisions to be judged as unenforceable.

Effectively, a mediator may have to testify on 'without prejudice' matters against their will, despite the parties' prior agreement not to do so. Consequently, the parties' contractual agreement regarding confidentiality would offer feeble protection of mediation privacy.²⁹

Therefore, it is key that any efforts to craft appropriate protection for confidential mediation communications address two baseline questions: first, what communications should be protected from disclosure of any kind, and second, what testimonial immunity the mediator should have.³⁰

5. The perspective in England & Wales

In the UK, there is no legislative framework to govern the status of mediation, its parties or the mediator, as is the case in some other jurisdictions.³¹

²⁸ Justice Briggs, 'Mediation Privilege?' (2009) 159 NLJ 506, 507.

²⁹ Anderson (n 2) 718.

³⁰ Owen V. Gray, 'Protecting the Confidentiality of Communications in Mediation' (1998) 36 Osgoode Hall L J 667, 701.

³¹ Allen, *Mediation Law and Civil Practice* (n 3) 49.

Generally, the courts in England & Wales are reluctant to lift the veil of mediation confidentiality. In the landmark case of *Halsey v. Milton Keynes NHS Trust*³², Dyson LJ remarked that if a dispute is not settled through mediation, it is not a matter for the court, and in order to respect the confidentiality and integrity of the process, the courts should not investigate why the process did not result in an agreement.³³

The UK Supreme Court confirmed in *Oceanbulk Shipping & Trading SA v. TMT Asia Ltd*³⁴ that ‘without prejudice’ negotiations can be used to establish background facts to understand the true meaning of the negotiated settlement. The problem with this is determining whether evidence is being put forward to prove an objective fact known to the parties or to establish the meaning of the contract because only the former is admissible.³⁵ In *Excelsior Group Productions Ltd v. Yorkshire Television Ltd*³⁶, the courts acknowledged that the line between what is admissible and inadmissible regarding pre-contractual negotiations is ‘so fine it almost vanishes’. In *Cumbria Waste Management Ltd v. Baines Wilson*³⁷ (“*Cumbria Waste Management*”), the Court had to decide whether disclosure of documentation could be ordered against one party’s wishes because of an exception to the ‘without prejudice’ privilege. The court found that it would be wrong to order the disclosure of the mediation documents. Therefore, the parties had a joint, but not several, right to waive the ‘without prejudice’ privilege.³⁸

³² *Halsey v. Milton Keynes NHS Trust* [2004] EWCA Civ 576, [2004] 1 WLR 3002.

³³ *ibid* [14].

³⁴ *Oceanbulk Shipping & Trading SA v. TMT Asia Ltd* [2010] UKSC 44, [2011] 1 AC 662.

³⁵ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 252.

³⁶ *Excelsior Group Productions Ltd v. Yorkshire Television Ltd* [2009] EWHC 1751 (Comm) [25].

³⁷ *Cumbria Waste Management Ltd v. Baines Wilson* [2008] EWHC 786 (QB).

³⁸ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 255.

Deputy High Court Judge, Mr Stuart Isaacs QC, remarked in the case of *Brown v Rice* that perhaps in the future, a distinct mediation privilege will be required to be considered by either the legislature or the courts.³⁹ Subsequently, Kirkham J remarked in *Cumbria Waste Management* that, either based on the ‘without prejudice’ rule or as an exception to the general rule that confidentiality is not a bar to disclosure, the courts should generally support the mediation process by refusing to order disclosure of documents and communications within a mediation.⁴⁰

This suggests that the English courts may be willing to rule that a specific mediation privilege exists. However, *Cumbria Waste Management* is a first-instance decision, and a court of appeal decision or statutory privilege is essential to interpret the complexities of mediation confidentiality in England and Wales.⁴¹ There is no certainty over the concept of ‘mediation privilege’, and *Cumbria Waste Management* leads us to question whether statutes should invent mediation privilege.⁴² Allen has also highlighted that this uncertainty is challenging for mediators as they do not know the precise boundaries of confidentiality, which lies at the heart of the success of the process.⁴³

However, the most recent jurisprudence highlights a different scenario. In *Pentagon Food Group Ltd and others v B Cadman Ltd*⁴⁴, HHJ Tindal made obiter comments on whether the enhanced importance of mediation generally justifies a more enhanced form of ‘mediation

³⁹ *Brown v. Rice* [2007] EWHC 625 (Ch) [20].

⁴⁰ *Cumbria Waste Management* (n 35) [30].

⁴¹ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 255.

⁴² Allen, *Mediation Law and Civil Practice* (n 3) 269.

⁴³ *ibid.*

⁴⁴ *Pentagon Food Group Ltd and others v B Cadman Ltd* [2024] EWHC 2513 (Comm).

privilege' beyond the 'without prejudice' privilege. He stated that he does not support the view that 'mediation privilege' is distinct from 'without prejudice' privilege.⁴⁵

6. California and the case for 'absolute confidentiality'

The purpose of the *Uniform Mediation Act*⁴⁶ in the United States is to ensure that mediation communications remain confidential to make mediation a fairer, more effective and more attractive means to settle disputes.⁴⁷ It aims to uphold principles of procedural fairness, process integrity and informed party consent throughout the mediation process. Many US states have refused to adopt the Act because existing state mediation laws dealing with confidentiality are already much stronger than the Act.⁴⁸ For example, the Act does not provide for the confidentiality of caucus sessions or the general duty of confidentiality about outside parties, leaving it to the parties to contract for this protection.⁴⁹ Some US states have resisted implementing the Act on the basis that courts should maintain the right to circumvent the confidentiality privilege where the interests of justice require it.⁵⁰

California is an example of a state that has gone above and beyond to protect mediation confidentiality. California has not adopted the Act into its legislative framework and relies on its Evidence Code⁵¹ to govern the confidentiality of mediation proceedings. In *Rojas v.*

⁴⁵ *ibid* [60].

⁴⁶ *Uniform Mediation Act* 2003.

⁴⁷ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 278.

⁴⁸ Douglas Golann and Joseph Folberg, *Mediation: The Roles of Advocate and Neutral* (3rd edn, Wolters Kluwer 2016) 346-47.

⁴⁹ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 291.

⁵⁰ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 289.

⁵¹ *California Evidence Code*.

*Superior Court*⁵², the California Supreme Court overturned the Court of Appeal's ruling that had devised an exception to mediation confidentiality to help plaintiffs in a subsequent proceeding access documents that were held as a non-appealable finding of fact, created exclusively for the mediation. The Supreme Court held that the confidentiality of mediation communications is absolute. This absolute protection given to mediation confidentiality has been criticised by the court in *Wimsatt v Superior Court*, which described it as leading to "harsh and inequitable consequences"⁵³.

Rojas and the jurisprudence that has followed present the dilemma when the policy requiring parties to disclose all relevant evidence conflicts with the policy supporting mediation confidentiality.⁵⁴ It has also been suggested that some provisions of the Act are hostile to the areas of practice that made mediation the popular process it has become. Mediation's key attractions include its diversity and adaptability. While it is reasonable to expect some consistency when participating in mediation, mediation must adapt to the needs of the parties and the parameters of the dispute being mediated.

Experience from the United States shows that very few cases involving confidentiality issues end up in court. Most reported cases arise from court-ordered mediation programmes, where parties are forced to participate, suggesting that there is generally better compliance when the process is private and voluntary.⁵⁵

⁵² *Rojas v. Superior Court* 33 Cal 4th 407 (2004).

⁵³ *Wimsatt v Superior Court* 152 Cal App 4th 137 (2007), 164.

⁵⁴ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 283.

⁵⁵ Golann and Folberg, *Mediation: The Roles of Advocate and Neutral* (n 48) 345-46.

7. Looking ahead: how do we approach reform?

There is a well-established need for mediation confidentiality, yet absolute mediation confidentiality seems a bridge too far. On the other hand, it has been suggested that the exceptions to it are so numerous that they almost erode mediation confidentiality.⁵⁶

An approach discussed in English cases such as *Brown*⁵⁷ and *Cumbria Waste Management*⁵⁸ is a distinct mediation privilege that can appreciate the nature of the process and protects mediation evidence and communications made during the process. It should be noted that mediation privileges do not bar disclosure outside court proceedings; therefore, the privilege does not equate to comprehensive confidentiality.⁵⁹ A generalised formulation recognising a mediation privilege would protect virtually all mediation communications. When judges need confidential information, courts will have more leeway in deciding whether to allow it than to stick to strict exceptions.⁶⁰

It is proposed that a distinct mediation privilege be introduced in England and Wales to offer clearer and more consistent protection for mediation communications. This privilege would uphold the integrity of the mediation process while permitting limited exceptions where disclosure is necessary to prevent injustice. Drawing on international models, the suggested mediation privilege would protect confidential communications but allow courts to assess competing public policy interests on a case-by-case basis. This approach can ensure the

⁵⁶ Lawrence Freedman and Michael Prigoff, 'Confidentiality in mediation: the need for protection' (1986) 2(1) *Ohio State Journal on Dispute Resolution* 37, 40.

⁵⁷ *Brown v. Rice* [2007] EWHC 625 (Ch).

⁵⁸ *Cumbria Waste Management* (n 35).

⁵⁹ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 290.

⁶⁰ Ronán Feehily, 'Confidentiality in Commercial Mediation: A Fine Balance (Part 2)' [2015] *J S Afr L* 719, 734.

flexibility that the mediation process needs by dealing with issues on a case-by-case basis and balancing public policy considerations, the requirements of the process, and the needs of participants and third parties.⁶¹ In light of obiter comments⁶² made in *Pentagon Food Group Ltd*, it would be interesting to see if future English cases further rule out the idea of a mediation privilege.

Finally, an essential part of the balancing act involves mediators, who continue to be targeted as potentially credible witnesses of what transpired in mediation proceedings.⁶³ The issue surrounding who the privilege belongs to, the mediation process or mediators should not be ignored. Briggs has proposed a "mediator secrets privilege," enabling the parties to confide in the mediator separately and receive assistance otherwise unavailable.⁶⁴

Like legal professional privilege, mediation secrets would be protected unless there was mediator misconduct. The scope of existing privileges may be broadened to incorporate mediators by applying the underlying policies.⁶⁵ Consequently, if such privilege were extended to mediators, the consent of both the mediator and the parties would be required to waive it.⁶⁶

The voluntary nature of the mediation process is a key principle, and whether the process will end in an agreement to end the dispute or not is a decision that is made by the parties.⁶⁷ This reflects the autonomy that parties have in the mediation process, and it is up to them whether

⁶¹ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 290.

⁶² *Pentagon Food Group Ltd* (n 43).

⁶³ Boule, *Mediation: Principles, Process, Practice* (n 14).

⁶⁴ Justice Briggs, 'Mediation Privilege?' (2009) 159 NLJ 550.

⁶⁵ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 258.

⁶⁶ *ibid.*

⁶⁷ Felix Steffek and Klaus J. Hopt (eds), *Mediation: Principles and Regulation in Comparative Perspective* (Oxford University Press 2013) 109.

to reach an agreement or not. This highlights the importance of ensuring that mediation communications remain confidential so that neither of the disputing parties misuse the autonomy and flexibility they have in a mediation setting.

8. Conclusion

Ongoing training and education for the judiciary can ensure that the courts embrace commercial mediation. By appointing specialised judges with mediation skills, parties will have the best chance to navigate mediation confidently and clearly.⁶⁸ This can be achieved by continuously developing guidelines established by the organisation under which mediation occurs. An advantage of this is that such guidelines are organic instruments and can be changed with relative frequency by the relevant organisation to reflect the changing nature of the process and the legal framework in which it operates.⁶⁹

Due to the unique and future-facing nature of mediation, the reforms proposed adopting a middle ground, upholding confidentiality, and flexibly balancing it with the justice system's interests. This discussion reflects the importance of an integrated approach to balancing public policy interests in mediation confidentiality. Confidentiality is a crucial and inevitable part of mediation, and it is key to regulate it justly and sensibly.

⁶⁸ *ibid.*

⁶⁹ Feehily, *International Commercial Mediation* (n 4) 267.

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